

Filename	NO-URBAN experiment	AH0 experiment	AH300 experiment	Description
TIME_MEAN_2m-T_experiments.nc	2mT_NOURBAN	2mT_AH0	2mT_AH300	Hourly mean 2m temperature averaged over all cases
TIME_MEAN_10m-WIND_experiments.nc	10M_U_NOURBAN	10M_U_AH300	10M_U_AH300	Hourly mean 10m wind (U,V) averaged over all cases
	10M_V_NOURBAN	10M_V_AH300	10M_V_AH300	
TIME_MEAN_RAIN_experiments.nc	rain_NOURBAN	rain_AH0	rain_AH300	Daily mean rainfall averaged over all cases
TIME_MEAN_Verticalintegrated_Specific-humidity_experiments.nc	SH_NOURBAN	SH_AH0	SH_AH300	Hourly mean vertical integrated specific humidity averaged over all cases